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Impact of Communication Routes on the Economy and their Types

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Abstract: *Communication routes play an important role in the development of social production. The economic development of the country, the growth of the national economy, the development of external and internal economic relations, depends on the clear functioning of communication routes.*

Key words: *trade routes, military roads, state roads, Railways, Motorways, Roads of communication in water hazards, Airways, Industrial roads, Economic roads, City roads and streets.*

Introduction: People's lives, their mutual relations, organization of work, treatment and recreation, exchange of cultural wealth, meeting the need for industrial and food goods - all these are connected with more communication channels.

Ways of communication are closely related to the physical existence of a person and the history of human society. During the primitive community system, people satisfied their transportation needs with simple means. People carry their own food, labor tools, materials for making clothes or creating comfortable living conditions, as well as fuel by themselves or by training various animals. transporters. With the development of human society, among the types of transport, sea and river transport began to develop first. Later, land-based vehicles began to develop. One of the greatest achievements of mankind is the invention of the wheel in Mesopotamia, 3500 BC. Scientists say that the wheel first appeared in Central Asia. The appearance of the wheel laid the foundation for the appearance of the vehicle. By the time of feudalism, the main means of transport was the horse-cart,

and with the development of industry, transport also developed, first steam ships, steam locomotives, land-moving steam cars, and later steam airplanes were created. The development of transport, in turn, led to the development of communication routes.

The beginning of the construction of communication roads in the history of mankind is understood as the conscious preparation of roads for multiple use. People have chosen a way to hunt in groups. Trails appeared as a result of repeated walking along this road. At that time, the adaptation of the road for movement was limited to the removal of stones and branches that interfered with bringing prey. When the slave states began to appear, they faced 2 problems, that is, first, to ensure the conquest of neighboring lands, to enslave people, and then to use them to suppress rebellions. The slave society had the following types of roads:

1. trade routes;
2. military roads;
3. State roads: to send messengers, for the passage of soldiers, to bring booty, to manage the state.

roads intended for religious ceremonies (prayer or solemn processes) (in front of the palace, madrasa). Ancient trade routes appeared at the beginning of the Bronze Age. The Great Silk Road appeared in the II century BC and was used for 1300 years. The Silk Road started from Arab countries and went to China through Central Asia. During the time of Genghis Khan, this road was not used for 300 years.

The conducted investigations show that in the 10th-11th centuries BC there was a "Royal Road of the Khorezm Shahs", which continued from Urgench to the Urals and the Volga. There is a caravanserai and wells on this road every 25 km (one day's journey of the caravan). Roads were required to be smooth in places where religious ceremonies were held, people gathered in large numbers, and solemn ceremonies were held. The Roman Empire had 90,000 km of stone paved highways. Taking into account dirt and gravel roads, the length of the road networks of the Roman Empire was 250-300 thousand km. The road networks of the Roman Empire consisted of a well-thought-out system that connected large centers. Rome was a junction of roads connecting all regions. The development of industry increased the demand for transportation of raw materials, fuel and finished products. At the beginning of the 19th century, roads in Europe were in a very bad condition. In France, J. Trezage proposed a new layer of pavement. After that, Mac Adam from Scotland (1756-1836) continued this work.

In 1871, the first asphalt pavement was laid in the United States. Asphalt roads increased in cities. With the development of cars, road construction norms and rules have also changed. The first specifications were published in 1931 and the next in 1934. 1938 "Technical conditions for building bridges and roads" was approved. Road construction has a long history. Road structures and their construction methods have changed in various aspects of human history. The first cobblestone roads were built in the center of the cities in places where religious ceremonies were held and on the streets. Communications is a multi-faceted and complex business. Communication road networks transport - wagons, locomotives, ships, tankers, cars, containers, airplanes, sorting and cargo-passenger stations, railway stations, ports, airfields, various types of loading and unloading machines and equipment, is closely related to the activity of repair factories.

The classification of communication routes is as follows: Railways; Motorways; Roads of communication in water hazards; Airways; Industrial roads; Economic roads; City roads and streets.

Today, the total length of the highway network in the republic is 184,000 km, the length of public railways is 3,645 km, the air routes are 150,000 km, and the communication routes in water hazards

are 500 km. public roads are 71324 km, city roads and streets are 69929 km. The geographical location of the republic requires that the main transport corridors for entering the world market and developing foreign economic relations are roads and railways.

Each communication method has its own advantages and disadvantages. If railways are characterized by the ability to transport a large amount of cargo, then the low speed of movement compared to other means of communication is one of its disadvantages. Waterways have the capacity to transport large volumes of cargo, but it can only do so via waterways and not being able to deliver the cargo to the consumer's doorstep is one of its disadvantages. Roads are the most efficient way to transport small loads over short distances. The advantage of roadways is that they provide door-to-door service. The advantage of the air route is fast and accurate delivery of goods to the destination, but the disadvantage is the high cost of transportation.

Conclusion: At the beginning of the 20th century, connecting Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, Termez, Karshi, Andijan, Fergana and other cities in the territory of modern Uzbekistan, where several countries of Central Asia were located at that time, as well as the countries of Afghanistan and Iran There were 27,000 kilometers of roads connecting with the big cities.

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